

Open Science NL

Open Research Software and FAIR Data Advisory Panel

Meeting Agenda

18 May 2026, 15:00-17:00

Location: [MS Teams](#)

Attendees

- Ana Martinovici
- Andrew S. Hoffman
- Bogdana Huma
- Daniel S. Katz
- Efi Gkoumassi
- Erik van den Bergh – *from 16.11*
- Iza Witkowska
- Martine de Vos
- Morane Gruenpeter
- Santosh Ilamparuthi
- Thomas Pronk
- Mark van Assem (MvA), Co-Chair
- Marta Teperek (MT), Chair

Apologies:

- Ana Martinovici

Agenda

Welcome and introductions

MT welcomed everyone, which was followed by a round of introductions during which panel members highlighted their expertise and their view on challenges pertaining to open research software, hardware and FAIR data.

Expertise of panel members

It was noted that a representative from Universities of Applied Sciences and from a knowledge/research institute was currently missing in the panel composition and needed to be appointed as soon as possible. Panel members also discussed whether any content expertise was currently missing within the panel and concluded that sufficient expertise was present (additional recruitment was not necessary from that perspective).

It was agreed that:

- OSNL will launch a new call for nominations for panel members before the summer. Received applications will be discussed during the upcoming panel meeting on 12 October. Afterwards, the representatives from Universities of Applied Sciences and from a knowledge/research institute will be appointed as soon as possible, and the members to replace 50% of the current panel members (when their terms come to end), at the beginning of 2027.

16.40 – 16.45 – Changes to the Terms of Reference

The terms of reference document was changed to reflect that the panels were merged and also to add a sentence about removal of panel members in case of repeated absences (as discussed during the last panel meetings). Panel members are asked to indicate if any additional changes to the Terms of Reference need to be made. One suggestion is made to add an explanation of the process that happens when a member of the panel unexpectedly leaves/is removed.

Name of the panel

Given the expanded scope of the merged panel, the name of the panel should also change. Based on some discussion a consensus accepted by the group is to call the new panel a “Open Science NL Research Software, Hardware and Data Advisory Panel”. Panel members suggested that an acronym is proposed to refer to the panel.

Next meeting

During the next panel meeting (12 October 2026, 15.00 – 17.00, hybrid) the following will be discussed:

- Term duration of panel members
- Selection of new members from the applications received

Meeting closed at 16:53.